
Dalubhasang Guro Ng Pilipinas (DGNP): An Online Journal of Innovative Education

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Summary— The "Dalubhasang Guro ng Pilipinas (DGNP)" electronic journal represents a transformative leap in the Philippine educational system. It addresses the longstanding issue of limited accessibility and dissemination of valuable research findings of teachers in the Department of Education by providing a user-friendly, open-access platform that caters to educators, researchers, and policymakers. DGNP's rigorous peer-review process guarantees the publication of high-quality, evidence-based research, which is essential for implementing effective and innovative teaching practices. By embracing digital technologies, DGNP enhances the visibility and impact of research, fostering a collaborative community committed to continuous professional development and educational excellence. This initiative not only informs policy decisions with empirical evidence but also empowers educators with the latest insights and methodologies, driving substantial improvements in teaching and learning outcomes. As DGNP evolves, it aims to incorporate emerging educational trends and sophisticated analytics, solidifying its role as a cornerstone of educational innovation in the Philippines. Embracing DGNP is not just a step towards better education; it is a commitment to a future where every Filipino student can benefit from the highest standards of educational research and practice.

Keywords— innovation, open access journal, policy, research

I. OVERVIEW

Across the country, DepEd orders and memoranda guide public school teachers in research to improve teaching and learning processes. This initiative fosters a culture of continuous improvement and empowers teachers to contribute directly to advancing educational practices. By engaging in research, teachers can identify effective strategies, address classroom challenges, and share valuable insights with their peers, leading to a more dynamic and responsive educational system. MECS Order No. 24, Series of 1978, significantly intensified teacher-researcher training in each school division. This directive aimed to equip educators with the necessary skills and knowledge to conduct meaningful research, fostering a more robust and innovative educational environment. By enhancing the research capabilities of teachers, the order sought to ensure that educational strategies and practices are grounded in evidence-based findings, ultimately leading to improved student outcomes and a more effective education system. This initiative also encouraged a culture of inquiry and continuous professional development among educators, contributing to the overall advancement of the educational landscape. After two decades,

DECS Order No. 100, Series of 1998, established guidelines for granting incentives for promotion purposes to DECS personnel involved in research and development programs and projects. This order recognized the critical role that research and development play in advancing educational practices and outcomes. By offering incentives, the order aimed to motivate educators to actively engage in research initiatives, ensuring a continuous flow of innovative ideas and solutions within the education sector. These incentives rewarded individual achievements and fostered a culture of excellence and dedication to professional growth among DECS personnel. As a result, the order created a more dynamic and progressive educational system, where research and development are integral to its evolution and success. In 2003, with the issuance of Department Order No. 65, the institutionalization of research-based decision-making and policy formulation within the Department was realized. This landmark order emphasized the importance of grounding decisions and policies in rigorous research and empirical evidence. The Department aimed to enhance its educational initiatives' effectiveness, relevance, and impact by embedding research into the core decision-making processes. This approach ensured that the latest findings and best practices informed policies and promoted a data-driven analysis and continuous improvement culture. Consequently, the institutionalization of research-based decision-making marked a significant step towards creating a more adaptive, informed,

and responsive educational system that could better meet the evolving needs of students and educators alike. The Basic Education Research Fund was designed to empower educators and researchers by providing the necessary financial resources to conduct comprehensive studies on critical aspects of education. By identifying specific areas and topics for research, the order sought to address the most pressing issues and opportunities within the education system. These targeted research areas included but were not limited to, curriculum development, teaching methodologies, student assessment, inclusive education, and technology integration in classrooms. The establishment of BERF also highlighted the Department's recognition of research's essential role in informing and shaping educational policies and practices. By investing in research, the Department aimed to generate valuable insights that could drive continuous improvement and innovation in the education sector. This initiative encouraged a culture of inquiry among educators, fostering an environment where evidence-based practices could thrive. However, significant issues and challenges have emerged concerning the dissemination and accessibility of research findings. In the Davao City Schools Division, a group of research enthusiasts took the initiative to publish and distribute a printed research journal named KATIGAMAN from 2010 to 2015. This publication aimed to share valuable research insights and findings within the local educational community. The primary issues and challenges revolved around the limited reach and dissemination of information, which hindered the effective utilization of research findings as inputs for policy-making and quality management systems. This limitation constrained the potential impact of research on educational policies and posed barriers to integrating innovative practices into the broader educational framework. Additionally, generating and developing innovations from research outputs and findings is challenging, as their visibility in an open system is limited. This lack of accessibility hampers the utilization of valuable resources by teachers, school heads, and supervisors, thereby restricting the authenticity of educational innovations that could serve as effective strategies to simplify teaching and learning processes. Addressing these visibility issues is crucial for fostering a more dynamic and responsive educational environment where innovative practices can flourish and benefit all stakeholders involved in the education sector. To tackle these challenges effectively, continuous improvement processes must be embraced. Maximizing the dissemination of research results and findings is essential to ensure a more profound understanding of their implications. Adopting electronic journal publications can significantly enhance accessibility for teachers, school heads, supervisors, and all stakeholders. This approach facilitates the sharing of ideas internationally and promotes the adoption of perspectives to achieve effective and efficient continuous improvement in educational practices. By leveraging electronic platforms, the academic community can foster a culture of innovation and collaboration, leading to enhanced teaching and learning outcomes across diverse settings.

II. INNOVATION DESCRIPTION

Dalubhasang Guro ng Pilipinas (DGNP) aims to serve as a premier electronic journal which can be accessed through

dgnp.org as seen in Figure 1, dedicated to advancing innovative practices, research, and insights in Philippine education. It seeks to provide a platform for educators, researchers, policymakers, and stakeholders to share and collaborate on transformative educational strategies and methodologies that enhance teaching and learning across the Philippines.

*c*Key Features:

1. **Open Access Platform:** DGNP operates as an open-access journal, ensuring that all published content is freely available to educators and researchers worldwide, through the utilization of Open Journal Systems by Public Knowledge Project.
2. **Multidisciplinary Focus:** Covers a broad spectrum of educational topics, including curriculum development, pedagogical innovations, educational technology, assessment methodologies, and more.
3. **Peer-Reviewed Articles:** A rigorous peer-review process ensures the quality and validity of published research, promoting evidence-based practices in education.
4. **Digital Format:** Published exclusively in digital format, allowing for interactive media, multimedia integration, and easy accessibility across various devices.

1. Components

1. **Website Interface:** User-friendly interface for browsing, searching, and accessing published articles and resources.
2. **Submission System:** Online submission portal for authors to submit their research papers and articles as seen in Figure 2.
3. **Editorial Board:** Composed of education experts who oversee the review and publication process.
4. **Archives:** Comprehensive archives of past issues and articles for reference and historical tracking.

2. Functionalities

1. **Article Publication:** Authors can submit original research papers, case studies, literature reviews, and innovative practices related to education.
2. **Peer Review:** A robust peer-review system ensures rigorous evaluation of submissions for scientific rigor, relevance, and contribution to the field.
3. **Interactive Media:** Integration of multimedia elements such as videos, interactive graphs, and simulations to enhance content delivery and engagement.
4. **Global Accessibility:** It facilitates global reach and collaboration among educators and researchers, fostering a diverse exchange of ideas and practices.

Fig. 1: Home Page

Fig. 2: Submission Page

3. Benefits

1. Knowledge Sharing: Facilitates dissemination of research findings and innovative practices to a global audience, promoting knowledge exchange and collaboration.
2. Professional Development: Supports continuous professional development among educators by providing access to current research and best practices.
3. Policy Influence: Influences educational policy-making by providing evidence-based insights and recommenda-

tions from published research.

4. Application Areas

1. Academic Institutions: Used by educators and researchers in, and schools for research and professional development.
2. Policy-Making: Consulted by policymakers and educational leaders for evidence-based decision-making in education reform and policy development.
3. International Collaboration: Facilitates collaboration

among international researchers and institutions, promoting cross-cultural perspectives and innovative solutions.

5. Future Developments

1. **Enhanced User Experience:** Improve the platform's usability, interface, and accessibility features.
2. **Expanded Content:** Diversification of content to include emerging topics in education, such as AI in basic education, global citizenship education, and sustainable development and all topics and goals under MATATAG Curriculum.
3. **Integration of Analytics:** Utilization of analytics to track readership, citation impact, and article usage patterns for authors and researchers which is to be an improvement of what is in Figure 3.

III. INNOVATION STATEMENT

Dalubhasang Guro ng Pilipinas (DGNP) is a pioneering electronic journal dedicated to advancing educational innovation and research not just in the Department of Education but in the Philippines. Operating as an open-access platform with a multidisciplinary focus, rigorous peer-reviewed articles by a board of experts, and an exclusive digital format which can be accessed through dgnp.org, DGNP facilitates the dissemination of cutting-edge educational practices and insights. It is a pivotal resource for educators, researchers, policymakers, and stakeholders, promoting evidence-based approaches that enhance teaching, learning, and educational policy formulation in a global scale.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION PROCEDURE

a. Process Flow Framework

The process flow or framework of the innovation begins with identifying the learners' needs, primarily through assessments. Following this, learners are organized based on their abilities. Those who demonstrate proficiency are provided with leveled activities tailored to their skill level, while those encountering challenges are given the Multiplication Grid. Subsequently, they are guided through a three-step process on how to effectively utilize the provided resources. To ensure comprehension, learners' understanding is assessed, and additional support is offered to address any confusion or uncertainties. Those requiring further assistance engage in guided activities, whereas those showing progress are encouraged to undertake independent practice to reinforce their newly acquired skills.

The steps are interconnected and sequentially build upon each other, facilitating a smooth and efficient operation of the innovation process. By following a structured and methodical order, each step informs and influences the next, ensuring a cohesive progression toward the goal. This approach enables effective coordination, minimizes disruptions, and maximizes the effectiveness of the innovation implementation, leading to improved outcomes and greater success in achieving the desired objectives.

b. Process Flow

Access and discovery on the DGNP platform are facilitated through a user-friendly website interface, allowing educators, researchers, and stakeholders to explore a diverse array of educational topics. These topics, categorized under curriculum development, pedagogical innovations, educational technology, and assessment methodologies, provide a comprehensive resource for users. Authors, including educators and researchers, submit their articles and research papers via the online submission system, where a rigorous peer-review process conducted by the editorial board ensures academic rigor and quality. Accepted articles are published in digital format, making them easily accessible and allowing for multimedia integration. The DGNP platform ensures that published content is freely accessible globally, promoting the dissemination of innovative educational practices and research findings.

DGNP also serves as a global hub for knowledge sharing among educators, researchers, policymakers, and stakeholders interested in Philippine education. It facilitates collaboration and networking opportunities, enabling users to engage in discussions, share insights, and build partnerships. Educators and researchers use DGNP for continuous learning, staying updated on current educational trends, research methodologies, and innovative teaching practices. The platform supports professional development by offering evidence-based insights and resources for improving teaching and learning outcomes.

Policymakers and educational leaders utilize research published on DGNP to inform evidence-based policy decisions and educational reforms. Contributions from DGNP articles play a role in assessing the impact of educational policies and initiatives. DGNP encourages user feedback and engagement through interactive features and discussion forums, and this feedback informs continuous improvements to the platform, enhancing user experience and content relevance. Looking to the future, DGNP aims to expand its content to include emerging educational topics and trends relevant to Philippine education, promoting community engagement by fostering collaboration, discussion, and shared learning experiences among users.

c. Project Management

The project management system for Dalubhasang Guro ng Pilipinas (DGNP) begins with project initiation, where the objectives, scope, and stakeholders are defined to establish the mission of advancing educational innovation and research in the Philippines. A detailed project plan is developed during the planning phase, outlining timelines, milestones, and resource allocations necessary for platform development and content creation. Risk assessment is conducted to anticipate technological issues and content quality control challenges. In the execution phase, content guidelines are established for article submission and peer review, alongside collaboration with IT specialists to customize the digital platform. An editorial board is formed to oversee the peer-review process and publication schedule. Monitoring and control involve tracking project progress and ensuring adherence to timelines and quality standards through continuous feedback. The closure phase includes a comprehen-

Fig. 3: Analytics

Fig. 4: Structural Framework

sive launch strategy to promote DGNP and evaluate its impact based on metrics like user engagement and publication frequency. Post-project evaluation identifies lessons learned for future enhancements, ensuring ongoing improvement and effectiveness in promoting evidence-based educational practices through DGNP.

d. Timeline

The timeline for the project innovation Dalubhasang Guro ng Pilipinas (DGNP) will commence in SY 2024-2025 and onwards, serving Philippine Public School Teachers and Non-Teaching Personnel and educators.

e. Resource Utilization

Dalubhasang Guro ng Pilipinas (DGNP) is a valuable resource for teachers through several key avenues. Firstly, operating as an open-access electronic journal ensures that teachers have unrestricted access to a wealth of educational resources and research findings without financial barriers, enabling them to stay informed about the latest educational trends and methodologies. The journal's multidisciplinary coverage spans curriculum development, pedagogical innovations, educational technology, and assessment methodologies, catering to diverse teaching contexts and professional development needs. Rigorous peer-review processes

Fig. 5: Utilization Process Flow

uphold the credibility and reliability of published content, empowering teachers to make informed decisions in their instructional practices and educational interventions. Published in digital format, DGNP integrates multimedia elements such as videos, interactive simulations, and graphics, enriching learning experiences and providing teachers with dynamic resources to enhance student engagement and outcomes. Teachers engage in continuous professional development by accessing evidence-based practices and innovative strategies aligned with current educational standards and research. Moreover, DGNP's influence extends to educational policies and advocacy efforts, where teachers can leverage research findings to advocate for beneficial changes in curricula, instructional methods, and academic policies. The platform also fosters a collaborative community of educators, researchers, and stakeholders, facilitating peer-to-peer learning, sharing of insights, and collective problem-solving. Ultimately, Dalubhasang Guro ng Pilipinas (DGNP) plays a pivotal role in empowering teachers with accessible, credible, and innovative resources that support their professional growth and enhance their impact on student learning and development.

f. Progress Monitoring

Monitoring Dalubhasang Guro ng Pilipinas (DGNP) involves systematic oversight to ensure the platform's effectiveness and impact on educational innovation. Initially, monitoring focuses on tracking platform usage metrics such as user

engagement, article submissions, and publication frequency to gauge its relevance and reach among teachers and educational stakeholders. Quality assurance measures are integral, ensuring that published content maintains high standards through ongoing assessment and feedback mechanisms from users and peer reviewers. Continuous evaluation of user feedback helps identify areas for improvement in content relevance, platform functionality, and user experience, ensuring that DGNP remains responsive to the evolving needs of educators. Additionally, periodic reviews assess the platform's contribution to advancing educational practices and influencing policy decisions, validating its role in promoting evidence-based teaching strategies and educational reforms in the Philippines.

V. SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

I intend to consistently incorporate the Multiplication Grid into my teaching practices by reintroducing it to my students each year. This ensures that more students have the opportunity to benefit from its use. Additionally, I will store the grids in an accessible location to ensure they are readily available for use when needed. By reintroducing the innovation yearly and keeping it accessible, there is a consistent provision of support for students' multiplication skills. This reduces the risk of discontinuity in the use of the innovation and helps maintain its effectiveness over time.

This may involve incorporating feedback from teachers and students to make necessary improvements, such as refin-

Aspects	Strategies
Financial Sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Diversify funding sources: government grants, educational institutions, corporate sponsorships, philanthropic organizations. - Introduce premium subscription models for additional features. - Seek sustainable revenue streams while maintaining open access.
Partnerships and Collaborations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establish strategic partnerships with educational institutions, government agencies, and international organizations. - Collaborate on joint research initiatives and educational programs. - Expand content and reach through partnerships.
Community Engagement and Support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement robust feedback mechanisms to improve platform features and content relevance. - Offer professional development workshops and certifications aligned with DGNP content. - Engage users through webinars and community events.
Technology and Infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continuously upgrade and update the digital platform for scalability, security, and compatibility. - Ensure accessibility across devices and internet connections. Invest in emerging technologies to enhance user experience.
Impact Assessment and Evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop key performance indicators (KPIs) to measure user engagement, article citations, and policy influence. - Conduct periodic reviews and evaluations to assess educational impact. - Adapt strategies based on evaluation findings.
Advocacy and Visibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Launch targeted marketing campaigns to raise awareness among teachers, policymakers, and stakeholders. - Use research findings and success stories to advocate for evidence-based educational practices. - Promote DGNP's impact through conferences and publications.
Capacity Building and Succession Planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide ongoing training and development opportunities for team members and stakeholders. - Establish a succession plan to ensure continuity in leadership and operations. - Preserve institutional knowledge and sustain long-term impact.

Fig. 6: Innovation Output/Outcomes

ing the design of the grid or adding supplementary resources to enhance learning experiences. Collaboration with educational experts and researchers can provide insights into innovative teaching methodologies and instructional practices to continuously enhance innovation. The innovation may lead to a more inclusive learning environment where students

of diverse learning styles and abilities can thrive, ultimately contributing to broader academic success and achievement.

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